

(De)legitimizing conquest and usurpation in Geoffrey Keating's *Foras Feasa ar Éirinn* and John Lynch's *Cambrensis Eversus*: Classical, Irish and European contexts

Feliks Levin

The issues of conquest and usurpation were central to discussions of sovereignty, political legitimacy and claims to land and property in seventeenth-century Ireland.¹ On the one hand, English rule, identity, and landholding in Ireland were based on the legacy of the twelfth-century Anglo-Norman conquest. On the other, Irish Gaelic claims that they had had independent statehood and a civilized polity prior to Henry II's invasion were dismissed by British authors, starting from the twelfth-century historian Gerald of Wales, because of the absence of legitimate hereditary succession in Ireland.² This absence, in the opinion of early modern English writers,³ testified to the tyrannical and barbarous nature of the Gaelic polity,

¹ Cf. Marc Caball, *Poets and Politics: Continuity and Reaction in Irish Poetry, 1558-1625* (Cork: Cork University Press, 1998), 83-152; Bernadette Cunningham, *The World of Geoffrey Keating: History, Myth and Religion in Seventeenth-Century Ireland* (Dublin: Four Courts Press, 2000), 141-58; Bart Van Es, "Discourses of Conquest: "The Faerie Queene", the Society of Antiquaries, and "A View of the Present State of Ireland", *English Literary Renaissance* 32, no. 1 (2002): 118-51; Ian Campbell, *Renaissance Humanism and Ethnicity before Race: The Irish and the English in the Seventeenth Century* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2013); James Michael Greaney, "History and Identity in Restoration Ireland, 1660-91," PhD diss. (Trinity College Dublin, 2022), 75-104.

² Giraldus Cambrensis, "Topographia Hibernica," in *Giraldi Cambrensis opera. Volume V*, ed. by James Dimock (London: Longmans, Green, Reader, and Dyer, 1867), 3-201, at 169, 188.

³ e.g. *Great Deeds in Ireland: Richard Stanihurst's De rebus in Hibernia Gestis*, ed. John Barry, Hiram Morgan (Cork: Cork University Press, 2013), 110-5; William Camden, "Hibernicorum mores veteres et recente," in *Britannia (1607)* with an English translation by Philemon Holland, ed. by Dana Sutton, § 3; John Davies, "A Discovery of the True Causes Why Ireland was Never Entirely Subdued nor Brought under Obedience of the Crown of England until the Beginning of his Majesty's Happy Reign (. . .) 1612," in *Ireland under Elizabeth and James the First*, ed. Henry Morley (London: Routledge, 1890), 217-342, at 322-3.

characterized by constant violent seizures of power and the arbitrary rule of the lord over the people. It also legitimized political reform in Ireland as well as the dispossession and political alienation of Gaelic and Gaelicized Old English lords.⁴

Contemporary scholarship often overlooks the fact that Irish Catholic authors who associated the origins of the Irish constitution with the pre-Anglo-Norman past were equally concerned with forceful acquisition of power before and after the twelfth-century invasion. This paper examines two authors of Old English background, Geoffrey Keating (1580-1644) and John Lynch (1599-1677), whose works reflect on the role of conquest and usurpation in Irish history—the Irish-language *Foras Feasa ar Éirinn* (1634-5)⁵ and the Neo-Latin *Cambrensis Eversus* (1662)⁶. In their comprehensive accounts of Irish history, they suggest alternative representations of the Irish past in contrast to English colonial narratives about Ireland. In this article I will contextualize their ideas on conquest and usurpation from the perspective of Gaelic, European, and Classical political thought, which have rarely been discussed in a comparative context, with the exception of Bernadette Cunningham’s comparative study of the two works that will be examined here.⁷ Despite the fact that Cunningham insightfully analyses Keating’s and Lynch’s ideas on kingship, parliament, and property rights in light of contemporary political affairs in Ireland, she does not place the multifaceted issue of violent acquisition of power in both narratives within the context of Irish Gaelic and European political

⁴ Nicholas Canny, *Making Ireland British, 1580–1650* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001), 1-58; Rory Rapple, *Martial Power and Elizabethan Political Culture: Military Men in England and Ireland, 1558–1594* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009), 162-99.

⁵ All text and translation of *Foras Feasa ar Éirinn* is taken from David Comyn and Patrick Dineen (eds.), *Foras Feasa ar Éirinn: the History of Ireland*, vol. I-IV (London: Irish Texts Society, 1908), henceforward *FFÉ*.

⁶ All quotations from *Cambrensis Eversus* are taken from Matthew Kelly (ed), *Cambrensis eversus, seu potius Historia fides in rebus Hibernicis Giraldo Cambrensi abrogata, . . .* vol.I-III (Dublin: Printed for the Celtic Society, 1851-2), henceforward *Cambrensis Eversus*.

⁷ Bernadette Cunningham, “Representations of King, Parliament, and the Irish People in Geoffrey Keating’s *Foras Feasa ar Eirinn* and John Lynch’s *Cambrensis Eversus* (1662),” in *Political Thought in Seventeenth-Century Ireland: Kingdom or Colony*, ed. Jane Ohlmeyer (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000), 131-54.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

discourses. This article will suggest a more nuanced reading of Keating's and Lynch's conceptions of forceful acquisitions of power and will challenge Cunningham's argument about the presence of the idea of 'elective' kingship in *Foras Feasa* and *Cambrensis Eversus*.

Keating and Lynch came from the same ethnic and intellectual background. They were born into Gaelicized Old English families, conversant in the vernacular literary canon, particularly Keating, and their overseas university clerical educations ensured that they were acutely aware of the Classics and contemporaneous trends in political thought.⁸ Both authors wrote histories of Ireland in order to refute the charges of barbarity laid against their people by the twelfth-century historian Gerald of Wales and his early modern followers. Keating's narrative traces Irish history from antediluvial times to the coming of the Anglo-Normans, whereas Lynch's text covered a lengthier period, including the events of the Irish Confederate Wars (1641-1653). There is a direct link between these two works: Lynch was well aware of *Foras Feasa* which he translated into Latin in the 1650s.⁹ Although Keating and Lynch might have expected their works to reach broader audiences, the readership of their works was different: the audience of Keating's *Foras Feasa* was primarily Irish-language circles familiar with Irish Gaelic historical lore and literature, whereas Lynch's *Cambrensis Eversus* targeted a European audience, whose perceptions about the Irish he wanted to change. The difference in intended audience between Keating's and Lynch's texts might also have affected the discursive models with which they interpreted the role of violent acquisitions of power in Irish history.

⁸ On Keating's and Lynch's educations and references to Gaelic, Classical, and contemporaneous European sources in their works cf. Cunningham, *The World of Geoffrey Keating*, 19-101; Nienke Tjoelker, "The *Alithinologia* by John Lynch. An Edition of Part of the Text with Introduction, Translation and Commentary," PhD diss., (University College Cork, 2010), iii-xxix; on education in early modern European universities, see: Hugues Beylard, "Douai," in *Les établissements des Jésuites en France depuis quatre siècles. Fasc. 6*, ed. P. Delattre (Enghien: Institut supérieur de théologie, 1950), 173-262, at 203-6; Michel Mollat, "Rouen," in *Les établissements des Jésuites en France depuis quatre siècles. Fasc. 14*, ed. P. Delattre (Enghien: Institut supérieur de théologie, 1955), 520-43, at 526-9.

⁹ Cunningham, *The World of Geoffrey Keating*, 187.

FELIKS LEVIN

Not only English Protestant authors but also Irish co-religionists were Keating's and Lynch's adversaries. The validity of the title of the English kings to Ireland and the legality of Old English claims to Irish offices and lands were contested in the Catholic camp, riven by interethnic and factional tensions in this turbulent period. Irish Gaelic emigré authors, such as Philip O'Sullivan Beare (1590-1636), Conor O'Mahony (1594-1656), and Richard O'Ferrall (d. 1663) considered Anglo-Norman conquest and Stuart rule in Ireland illegitimate. Moreover, O'Sullivan Beare and O'Ferrall emphasized the divisions between Catholics of Gaelic and Old English background, identifying the native Gaelic population of Ireland as the only true Irishmen to exercise the right to self-government, ecclesiastical offices, and property.¹⁰ Keating and Lynch belonged to a different discursive tradition which supported the Stuart dynasty and minimized the distinctions between Gaelic and Old English Catholics. Therefore, the challenge they grappled with was how to compose a counter-narrative of Irish history which would both defend the Irish Gaelic past and culture and assert the legitimacy of the English kings, particularly the Stuart Protestant dynasty, to rule Ireland, and the eligibility of the descendants of the medieval Anglo-Norman colonists to hold power and property there.

Both Keating and Lynch normalize violent acquisitions of power in Irish history representing it as a natural event. The idea of the normalcy of conquest and the forceful acquisition of the throne, in general, is expressed in the narrative and conceptual schemes of *Foras Feasa* which reflect traditional motifs and literary conventions. First, Keating inherits the narrative framework from the medieval pseudohistorical source *Lebor Gabála Éirenn* which revolves around the settlement of Ireland by different

¹⁰ Tadhg Ó hAnnracháin, "Though Hereticks and Politicians Should Misinterpret Their Goode Zeal": Political Ideology and Catholicism in Early Modern Ireland," in *Political Thought in Seventeenth-Century Ireland*, 155–75, at 158–63; Ian Campbell, "Alithinologia: John Lynch and Seventeenth-Century Irish Political Thought," PhD diss., (Trinity College Dublin, 2008), 69-84; Hiram Morgan, "'Making Ireland Spanish': the Political Writings of Philip O'Sullivan Beare," in *Making Ireland Roman: Irish Neo-Latin Writers and the Republic of Letters*, ed. Jason Harris, Keith Sidwell (Cork: Cork University Press, 2009), 86-108, at 89-93.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

tribes and the kingship from the Creation to the Anglo-Norman conquest.¹¹ As in *Lebor Gabála*, each invading tribe described in *Foras Feasa* takes Ireland by force and subdues its predecessors. The motif of ‘taking’ (*gabháil*) is also realized in the narrative formulae which introduce conquests of Ireland by various peoples and the coming to power of different kings. Keating frequently starts narrating the rule of individual kings with the following phrase: “*Do gabh X rioghacht/flaitheas Éireann*” (X seized the kingdom of Ireland/obtained sovereignty over Ireland). Therefore, accession to power in Ireland is framed in *Foras Feasa* as a forceful seizure.

Second, Keating legitimizes the violent seizure of power in Ireland through the principle ‘might is right’. Following Irish Gaelic literary conventions,¹² he depicts the sovereignty of Ireland as a prize awarded to the most deserving claimants in terms of military prowess, highlighting that only the strongest deserved the Irish high kingship. Explaining the claim to the Irish throne of the eleventh century king of Munster Brian Ború, who deposed Máel Sechnaill mac Domnaill, Keating emphasizes that succession in Ireland was often decided by force and that the title was an individual achievement rather than a hereditary inheritance.

*Óir ní hé an mac i n-áit an athar fá gnáth ag gabháil
fhlaitheasa Éireann, mar is follus as an stair anuas go ró
so, acht an tí fá mó oirbheart is arrachtas gníomh, is dó do
léighthí flaitheas Éireann.*

[. . .]

*Agus do bhrígh gurab é Brian fá mó oirbheart 'n-a aimsir
féin d'Éireannchaibh do thoghadar urmhór uaisle Éireann
ré ceannas na críche do ghabháil é, agus an mhéid díobh
nar aontuigh flaitheas Éireann da rochtainn, fá héigean
dóibh giall da n-aimhdheoin dó, agus fá héigean do*

¹¹ On Keating’s use of *Lebor Gabála*, see Anne Cronin, “Sources of Keating’s *Foras Feasa* ar Éirinn: 2, Manuscript Sources,” *Éigse* 5 (1945- 47): 122-135; Cunningham, *The World of Geoffrey Keating*, 65-9.

¹² Michelle O Riordan, *The Gaelic Mind and the Collapse of the Gaelic World* (Cork: Cork University Press, 1990), 105-17; Katharine Simms, *From Kings to Warlords: the Changing Political Structure of Gaelic Ireland in the Later Middle Ages* (Woodbridge: Boydell Press, 2000), 43.

FELIKS LEVIN

Mhaoilseachlainn flaitheas Éireann do thréigean is a léigean do Bhrian, amhail adubhramar.

For it was not the custom in Ireland that the son inherited sovereignty of Ireland from father, as is plain from the history up to this point, that the most skillful in action and exploit was permitted to obtain sovereignty of Ireland.

[. . .]

And since Brian was the most valorous of the Irish in his own time, the majority of the nobles of Ireland chose him to be the king of the country, and those who did not consent that the sovereignty over Ireland should be given to him were forced to submit to him against their will, and Maoilseachlainn was obliged to abandon the sovereignty over Ireland and cede it to Brian as we have said.¹³

The emphasis on conquest giving a valid title to land also enables Keating to fit the Anglo-Norman invasion of Ireland into the scheme of occupations. Keating's appeal to the right of conquest as a legitimating tool for supporting the claims of non-Gaelic lords tallies with contemporary trends in early modern Irish bardic poetry. For example, in the poem *Fearann cloidhimh críoch Bhanbha* ("The land of Banba is swordland") (1570s), dedicated to the Old English lord Seaán mac Oliver Bourke (d. 1580), Tadhg Dall Ó hUiginn leverages the narrative of *Lebor Gabála Éirenn* to argue that land title in Ireland was based effectively on force of arms. Various peoples were displaced by militarily stronger groups and, in this context, the claim of the Gaels as conquerors to Ireland was equated with that of the Anglo-Norman invaders.¹⁴

*§ 1. Fearann cloidhimh críoch Bhanbha,
bíoth slán cháich fá chomhardha
go bhfuil d'oighreacht ar Fiadh bhFáil
acht foirneart gliadh dá gabháil.*

¹³ *FFÉ*, III, 256-7.

¹⁴ For an analysis of the poem, see Caball, *Poets and Politics*, 145-7.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

§ 4 *Ní fuil do cheart ar chrích bhFáil
ag Macaibh Mileadh Easbáin,
's ní bhí ag gach gabháil dár gheabh,
acht sí d'fagháil ar éigean.*

§ 9 *Má tá gúr ghabhsad Gaoidhil
an gcrích bhfairsing bhforbhfaoidh,
do hathghabhadh i orthaibh,
sí ar n-athraghadh d'eachtronnchaibh.*¹⁵

The land of Banbha is but swordland:
let all be defied to show
that there is any inheritance to the Land of Fál
Save that of conquest by force of battle!

Neither the Sons of Mil of Spain
nor any who have conquered her
have any claim to the land of Fál
save that of taking her by force.

Although the Gaels conquered
the spacious, kindly land,
it was reconquered in despite of them,
and has passed into the power of foreigners.¹⁶

A similar argument for the legitimacy of Old English landholding in Ireland is found in the anonymous sixteenth-century poem *Seanoir cuilg cairt an Bhurcaigh* (“An old hand with the sword is the Burke’s charter”), which justifies the right of another Old English lord Richard Burke, second earl of Clanricarde, to possess territory in Connacht: *Cairt cloidhimh ca cairt is ferr* (“Charter of the sword, what charter is better?”).¹⁷ The early conquests of Ireland act as historical precedent for Burke’s territorial

¹⁵ Eleanor Knott (ed), *The Bardic Poems of Tadhg Dall Ó hUiginn (1550-1591)*. Vol. I: *Introduction and Text* (London: Irish Texts Society, 1922), 120-1.

¹⁶ Eleanor Knott (ed), *The Bardic Poems of Tadhg Dall Ó hUiginn (1550-1591)*. Vol. II: *Translation, Notes Etc.* (London: Irish Texts Society, 1922), 80.

¹⁷ “Seanoir cuilg cairt an Bhurcaigh”, *Bardic Poetry Database*, poem 1692, § 2. For an analysis of the poem, see Gregory R. Darwin, “Seanóir cuilg cairt an Bhúrcaigh (ca. 1550)”, *North American Journal of Celtic Studies* 8, no.2 (2024): 181-200, at 181-6.

FELIKS LEVIN

acquisition. Keating may not have been aware of these poems, but he likely counted on a similar reading of his narrative.

Nevertheless, Keating recognizes the importance of birthright alongside military valour for the acquisition of the Irish throne. For example, Brian Ború's legitimacy is enhanced by his royal blood (*fuil ríoghda*).

Nó ma's tré theacht fá bhrághaid Maoilsheachlainn i bhflaitheas na críche ar thogha urmhóir uaisle Éireann do gairfidhe anfhlaith dhe, féachadh an léagthóir cia córa anfhlaith do ghairm dhe ionáid anfhlaith do ghairm d'urmhór a dtáinig do ríogaibh Éireann do chlannaibh Mileadh. Óir ní tháinig an seachtmhadh fear díobh nach é marbhadh an ríogh roimhe do dhéanadh; agus ó nach gairmthear anfhlaith dhíobh, do bhrígh go dtángadar don fhuil ríoghda, tré mharbhadh na ríogh táinig rompa, mar an gcéadna, ar mbeith do Bhrian don fhuil ríoghda, ní hiontugtha anfhlaith air tré theacht fá bhrághaid Mhaoilsheachlainn, is nachar mharbh é, agus é ar a chumas, amhail do-nídís cách ris na ríogaibh do bhíodh rompa i bhflaitheas Éireann, amhail adubhramar.

Or if he should be called a tyrant for supplanting Maoilseachlainn in the sovereignty of the country, having been chosen by the majority of the Irish nobles, let the reader judge whether it be more just to call him a tyrant than to call the majority of the kings of Ireland who sprang from the children of Milidh tyrants. For not one in every seven of them gained the sovereignty who did not do so by killing the king who came before him ; and since they are not called tyrants, being of the royal blood, for killing the king who came before them, in the same way, since Brian was of the royal blood he should not be called a tyrant for having supplanted Maoilseachlainn, whom, though he was in his power, he did not kill, as other kings killed those who came before them in the sovereignty of Ireland, as we have said.¹⁸

¹⁸ *FFÉ*, III, 264-5.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

In this passage, Keating refutes the accusations of usurpation levelled against Brian Ború and other Irish kings by referring to their noble ancestry.¹⁹ Aristocratic pedigree is seen as more important than the manner in which the power is acquired. Keating highlights that nobility defines a person's entitlement to the Irish throne:

Is urusa a aithne ar an dteist-se do-bheirid na seanchaidhe ar Bhrian nar dhligtheach anfhlaith do ghairm dhe, óir ní do réir a thoile nó a neirt do rinne follamhnughadh na criche ré linn bheith i bhflaitheas dó, acht do réir reachta is dlighidh na criche. Óir is é is anfhlaith ann an tí do-ní follamhnughadh nó riaghlughadh do réir neirt is ní do réir cheirt; agus ó nach mar sin do rinne Brian, acht do réir cheirt is reachta, ní hiontugtha anfhlaith air.

It is very easy to infer from the testimonies the seanchas give of Brian that it would not be right to call him a tyrant (usurper), for it was not according to his will or his strength that he governed the country during his reign, but according to the country's laws and rules. For a tyrant (usurper) is one who governs and rules according to might and not according to right; and since it was not thus Brian acted, but according to right and law, he cannot be called a tyrant.²⁰

Here, Keating emphasizes that Brian Ború did not govern solely by might, like a conventional tyrant, but according to right (*ceart*) and law (*reacht*). He employs the concept of *ceart*, which in early modern Irish Gaelic political thought linked an entitlement to land and power with noble

¹⁹ Keating might have argued not only with the English opponents but also with Gaelic literati from the North who considered the deposition of Máel Sechnaill mac Domnaill illegal. For example, Lughaidh Ó Cléirigh (1580-1630) questioned the validity of the claim of the Munster king to high-kingship in the poem *Ro chuala ar thagrais a Thaidgh* (I have listened to your arguments, Tadhg). Lambert McKenna (ed.), *Iomarbhágh na bhfileadh = The Contention of the Bards* (London: Published for the Irish Texts Society by Simpkin, Marshall, Hamilton, Kent, 1918), 86, §237.

²⁰ *FFÉ*, III, 264-5.

FELIKS LEVIN

background.²¹ This concept enables Keating to find a certain logic in the transfer of power in Ireland. Irish kings legally deposed their predecessors because they had entitlement to the Irish throne derived from their ancestry, whereas martial exploits allowed their abstract right to kingship to be actualized. Two stanzas from Tuathal Ó hUiginn's ode (early fifteenth century) to Eoghan Ó Raghallaigh, lord of Breifne, similarly express the legitimacy of violence as the right to territory.

*Cairt eile ní iarrfa sibh
acht tú ar thoradh do ghaisgidh;
léim fa ghaoibh géara dod ghuin
séala dhaoibh ar do dhúthaigh.*

*An chraoiseach leathan sa láimh
's an colg a ceadcha Bholcáin
madh faigse hi budh hi an tsleagh
is i do chairtse an cloidheamh.²²*

Thou shalt seek no other charter
Except thy own reliance on thy gallantry;
To charge against the sharp spears that pierce thee
Is thy true charter to thy land.

The sharp spear in thy hand,
The blade from Vulcan's smithy,
The spear if it be nearer thee,
Thy sword—those are thy charter.²³

²¹ Brendan Kane, "The Nine Years' War in Ireland (1594–1603) as Problem of Government," in *Political and Religious Practice in the Early Modern British World*, ed. William J. Bulman, Freddy Cristóbal Dominguez (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2022), 181-202, at 188-93.

²² Lambert McKenna (ed.), *Aithdioghluim dána: a Miscellany of Irish Bardic Poetry, Historical and Religious, Including the Historical Poems of the Duanaire in the Yellow Book of Lecan*, I, vol. 37 (Dublin: Irish Texts Society, 1989), 122.

²³ Lambert McKenna (ed.), *Aithdioghluim dána: a Miscellany of Irish Bardic Poetry, Historical and Religious, Including the Historical Poems of the Duanaire in the Yellow Book of Lecan*. Edited with Translation, Introduction, Notes and Glossary, II, vol. 40 (Dublin: Irish Texts Society, 1940), 73.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

Ó hUiginn speaks to the competitive nature of land ownership in Ireland, suggesting that the claimant had to dominate adversaries militarily in order to assert the right to territory. Likewise, Keating rationalizes the violent acquisition of power in Ireland as a legal practice echoing a vernacular discourse of political legitimacy which foregrounds noble descent and military might as the main qualifications for rightful accession to the throne.²⁴

At the same time, Keating distinguishes between legitimate and illegitimate conquests. It is telling that those who are described as tyrants or usurpers (*anf(h)laith*) or as enslaving (*moghsaine, daoirse*) and oppressing (*anbhroid*) the native people are either hostile overseas foreigners (Fomorians,²⁵ Scandinavians,²⁶ and even some Anglo-Norman families²⁷) or domestic social inferiors (the ignoble tribe of Aithechthúatha who came to power after having murdered the high-king Fiachaidh Fionnoladh).²⁸ Keating here uses the concept of descent to separate outsiders (except for the descendants of the Anglo-Normans) and serfs from legitimate claimants to the Irish throne and land.

Keating devised alternative criteria for the Anglo-Normans and their descendants, whose *ceart* could be contested, to differentiate their conquest from other foreign invasions and to defend their status in Ireland. One such criterion was Keating's distinction between pagan and Christian conquest. The former brought destruction, the banishment of the native population and the extirpation of their language and culture, whereas the latter ensured the peaceful coexistence of the colonists with the indigenous population,²⁹

²⁴ This discourse is found in medieval and early modern legal tracts, historical writing, and bardic poetry. Joep Leerssen, *Mere Irish & Fíor-Ghael: Studies in the Idea of Irish Nationality, Its Development, and Literary Expression Prior to the Nineteenth Century* (Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publ. Co, 1986), 184-8; Caball, *Poets and Politics*, 25-9; Katharine Simms, *From Kings to Warlords*, 41-59; Bart Jaski, *Early Irish Kingship and Succession* (Dublin: Four Courts Press, 2013), 143-70; Kane, "The Nine Years' War", 190-1.

²⁵ *FFÉ*, I, 180-4.

²⁶ *FFÉ*, III, 22, 154, 158, 172-182.

²⁷ *FFÉ*, III 358, 366.

²⁸ *FFÉ*, II, 238-44.

²⁹ *FFÉ*, I, 34-36.

FELIKS LEVIN

and patronized the faith.³⁰ According to Keating, the Anglo-Norman invasion exemplified Christian conquest: except for several families, the conquerors did not do harm to the Gaels. Intermarriages between the two peoples and friendship also illustrate harmonious relationships between the colonizers and the colonized in *Foras Feasa*.³¹ Therefore, by emphasizing the manner of conquest and neighborly relationships between the colonists and the native population, Keating sets apart the Anglo-Norman conquest from previous foreign incursions and the oppressive English Protestant subjugation of Ireland, references to which are hidden between the lines of the narrative.

Another criterion which marked the right of the Anglo-Normans' descendants to land and power in Ireland was the length of their residence. Keating includes two groups in the list of rightful inhabitants (*áitightheori*): the Gaels who possessed lands in Ireland for almost three thousand years, and the Old English, who were in possession of Irish lands for more than four hundred years.³² The conceptual innovation of *Foras Feasa* was in associating nationality with birth and continuous residence within a certain territory, rather than with ancestry.³³ Judging by the use of the term *Éireannach* (Irish) which was applied only to inhabitants of Ireland, it appears that the land absorbed the waves of the invaders, making them Irishmen. For example, before arrival in Ireland, the Gaels are referred to either as Gaels or Scotie people (*cine Scuit*) in *Foras Feasa*.³⁴ In other words, only those conquerors, who became entrenched in Ireland and were not displaced by competitors, had the right to be called the Irish and hence to possess the lands. This logic justified the nativeness of the Old English, unlike recent Protestant newcomers.

In *Cambrensis Eversus*, John Lynch also normalizes the forceful acquisition of power in Ireland but from a comparative rather than a national

³⁰ *FFÉ*, III, 368.

³¹ *FFÉ*, I, 32-4.

³² *FFÉ*, I, 2.

³³ Cunningham, *The World of Geoffrey Keating*, 109-11; Cunningham, "Representations of King," 135-6.

³⁴ See *FFÉ*, II, 2-62, 78-96.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

perspective.³⁵ He admits that the strongest competitors seized the throne, violating the rules of hereditary succession, but their claims to power were not exclusively based on force, being supported by royal blood or other legal rights.³⁶ The argument about noble ancestry legitimizing the takeover of kingship may have been borrowed from *Foras Feasa*. However, Lynch's justification of political assassinations in Ireland centers on the universality of such precedents in world history rather than on their legality and normalcy in native practices. Lynch elucidates that there was nothing exceptional in killing predecessors in order to acquire power in those times.

Aliis admirationem, et mihi quoque non raro movit, quod ē memoratis jam Regibus, si non plerique, saltem quam plurimi, non suâ sed violenta morte sublatis; Et decessorem successor saepe saepius vita privavit . . . sic cum inhumana ilia Hibernorum consuetudo, aliis quoque nationibus per ea tempora familiaris fuisse deprehendatur, non est tantopere obstupescenda, nec tota tantae inhumanitatis culpa in solos Hibernos est conferenda, in cujus consortio, pleracque alias gentes Hibernos aequant, aut potius superant.

It has frequently been a matter of astonishment to me and to others, that of the aforementioned kings, at least a great number, if not most of them, died not from a natural but from a violent death, and that the successor quite often killed his predecessor . . . so when this inhuman custom of the Irish is discovered to have been common to all contemporary nations, it is not so much to be astonished at, nor is the whole guilt of such inhumanity to be assigned to the Irish alone, as other nations could rival the Irish in it, if not surpass them.³⁷

³⁵ Cunningham, "Representations of King," 140; Tishunin Evgeniï, "Reprezentatsiia vlasti nad Irlandiï v istoricheskom tractate Dzhona Lincha "Cambrensis Eversus" (1662)," *ISTORIYA* 13, iss. 1(2022): 2-14, at 3.

³⁶ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 324, 335.

³⁷ *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 100. The translation is my own.

Through a comparative perspective, Lynch de-exoticizes and relativizes violence in Gaelic Ireland, highlighting that the violent seizure of the throne was endemic to all nations during these times. He refers to brutal political murders from Roman and European (including English) history as precedents.³⁸ Lynch uses global contextualization of the peculiarities of succession in the Irish pre-Anglo-Norman history as an appeal to European readership,³⁹ for whom the Irish past becomes more intelligible through analogies, and as a device of forensic rhetoric, enabling him to expose the false assertions of Gerald Wales and his early modern followers, whose accusations against the Gaels could be applicable to other societies including the ones to which the critics of the Irish belonged.

The comparative antiquarian approach Lynch adopts towards Irish kingship may have been inspired by developments in both Irish and European intellectual culture. Lynch follows the work *De Hibernia et antiquitatibus ejus disquisitiones* (1654) by the Irish Protestant historian Sir James Ware (1594-1666), which he cites in *Cambrensis Eversus*. Placing Irish history in the European context,⁴⁰ Ware de-exoticizes Irish political assassinations by comparing them with similar precedents in Roman history.⁴¹ Besides that, Lynch was influenced by the growing interest in ethnology of observing customs, evinced by early modern European intellectuals who examined legal practices and political arrangements of the past and the present from a comparative viewpoint in order to identify continuities and changes, similarities and differences.⁴² This methodology

³⁸ *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 100-6; *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 324.

³⁹ Cunningham, "Representations of King," 140.

⁴⁰ Mark Empey, "Creating a Usable Past: James and Robert Ware," in *The Church of Ireland and Its Past*, ed. Mark Empey, Alan Ford, Miriam Moffitt (Dublin: Four Courts Press, 2017), 36-56, at 44-5.

⁴¹ James Ware, *De Hibernia et antiquitatibus ejus disquisitiones* (London: Typis J. Grismond, impensis Jo. Crook & Thomas, 1654), 15.

⁴² E.g. Julian Franklin, *Jean Bodin and the Sixteenth Century Revolution in The Methodology of Law and History* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1963), 68-79; Donald Kelley, "Altera Natura: The Idea of Custom in Historical Perspective," in *New Perspectives on Renaissance Thought: Essays in the History of Science, Education and Philosophy: in Memory of Charles B. Schmitt*, ed. John Henry, Sarah Hutton (London: Duckworth, 1990), 83-100; Peter N. Miller, "The Antiquary's Art of Comparison. Peiresc and "Abraxas"," in *Philologie und Erkenntnis. Beiträge zu*

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

can be found in *Methodus ad facilem historiarum cognitionem* (1566) by the French lawyer, historian, and political philosopher Jean Bodin (1530-96), and in *De Jure Belli ac Pacis* (1625) by the Dutch jurist Hugo Grotius (1583-1685), both of whom are frequently quoted by Lynch. These authors employ historically contingent comparisons of laws, customs, and political institutions of diverse peoples as a means of sustaining their arguments.

In contrast to Keating, Lynch does not acknowledge the legitimacy of the Anglo-Norman invasion of Ireland. In *Foras Feasa*, the history of the Irish kingship was viewed from the perspective of *translatio imperii*: the English kings inherited the power over Ireland from their Irish predecessors.⁴³ Conversely, *Cambrensis Eversus* states that the Irish kingship was disrupted after the Anglo-Norman invasion, with Ruaidhri Ó Conchubhair being the last Irish high king. According to Lynch, the sovereign power over Ireland was restored during the rule of James I Stuart, who possessed Gaelic pedigrees.⁴⁴ Similarly to Keating,⁴⁵ Lynch refuted the statements about the decay of Irish Christianity in the Middle Ages,⁴⁶ which Pope Adrian IV used to justify entrusting the authority over Ireland to Henry II to enforce the faith in the bull *Laudabiliter*. Lynch argues that the bull itself was a forgery⁴⁷ and, diverging from Keating,⁴⁸ emphasizes that the Pope had never had sovereignty over Ireland since the Irish king could not abdicate in favour of an alien.⁴⁹

Lynch also insists that the Anglo-Norman invasion failed to subdue the entire island of Ireland borrowing the argument from early Stuart New English official Sir John Davies (1569-1626). Davies highlighted that the

Begriff und Problem frühneuzeitlicher Philologie, ed. Ralph Häfner (Tübingen: Niemeyer, 2001), 57–94.

⁴³ Brendan Bradshaw, “Geoffrey Keating: Apologist of Irish Ireland,” in *Representing Ireland: Literature and the Origins of Conflict, 1534–1660*, ed. Brendan Bradshaw, Andrew Hadfield, Willy Maley (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1993), 166–191, at 174–8.

⁴⁴ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 52–66.

⁴⁵ *FFÉ*, III, 350–8.

⁴⁶ *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 336–60; 388–428; 504–10; 588–688; 724–70; *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 348–496.

⁴⁷ *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 430–66, 468–502.

⁴⁸ *FFÉ*, III, 6, 346–8.

⁴⁹ *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 490–2.

FELIKS LEVIN

Gaelic Irish had not been the subjects of the English kings until the accession of James I Stuart, obeying neither their laws, nor the magistrates appointed by them.⁵⁰ Both Davies and Lynch, employing a Bodinian definition of sovereignty,⁵¹ conclude that the English kings were only liege-lords and did not exercise sovereign power in Ireland for several hundred years.⁵² The conquest was only finalized during the reign of James I, who conferred subjecthood on the Gaelic Irish. Conceptualizing conquest in such a way and dismissing the examples of earlier foreign conquests of Ireland, Lynch represented his country as free from subjection to a foreign power throughout its entire history, which could be the source of pride for the Irish.⁵³

However, Lynch had to accept the outcomes of the conquest for the sake of constructing the political legitimacy of the Stuart dynasty and the Old English in *Cambrensis Eversus*. First, although James I possessed a hereditary right to the Irish crown on the basis of Gaelic descent,⁵⁴ the manner he acquired it—by means of ascending to the English throne—still tied him to the Anglo-Norman invasion. Lynch had to respond to his aforementioned Irish Catholic adversaries who dismissed Stuart claims to the Irish throne on account of the illegitimacy of the conquest alongside Protestant heresy.⁵⁵ Second, the Old English right of inheritance in

⁵⁰ Davies, “A Discovery of the True Causes,” 219, 222-3, 332-4; *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 52.

⁵¹ Ian Campbell, “Alithinologia: John Lynch,” 165-6. For Bodinian definition of sovereignty cf.: Jean Bodin, *Les six livres de la République* (Lyon: de l'imprimerie de Jean de Tournes, 1579), b.I, ch. VIII, X, 85-111, 147-74.

⁵² *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 522-6.

⁵³ *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 80-4, 436; *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 2-16, 22-8.

⁵⁴ Both Lynch and Keating believed in the existence of a separate Irish crown which had been possessed by the Irish high kings before the Anglo-Norman conquest and then inherited by the English monarchs. Lynch develops this topic particularly. *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 326-32. On the idea of Ireland as a distinct kingdom in the early modern Irish political discourse, cf. Breandán Ó Buachalla, *The Crown of Ireland* (Galway: Arlen House, 2006), 20-43; Feliks Levin, “Periferijnyj vzgljad na kompozitarnuju monarhiju: primer rannestjuartovskoj Irlandii,” in *Anglija i Evropa: ot srednih vekov k novomu vremeni. Sbornik statej k jubileju Sergeja Egorovicha Fedorova*, ed. Andrei Prokopiev (Saint Petersburg: Aletejja, 2023), 156-205, at 163-91.

⁵⁵ Campbell, “Alithinologia: John Lynch”, 158-72; 176-9, 194-205.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

contemporary Ireland owed its origins to the twelfth-century conquest. This right was questioned by O'Ferrall, who advocated against appointing Old English to ecclesiastical offices in the report on Irish affairs submitted in 1658 to the secretary of the congregation for the Propagation of Faith.⁵⁶ In *Cambrensis Eversus*, Lynch refutes his opponents, arguing that unjust conquest did not annul Stuart royal title or Old English land titles and offices.

Lynch resolves the dilemma of how to legitimize the royal title and claims to property derived from the invasion without legitimizing the invasion itself by detaching the origins of polity from its present. He places the kingdom of Ireland in the European context, highlighting that almost all European kingdoms were acquired by injustice, including the Roman empire.⁵⁷ By this, Lynch implied that unjust foundations of contemporary regimes did not make them illegitimate.

Lynch's pragmatic attitude towards the origin of political authority may have stemmed from his Catholic education based on the Jesuit model.⁵⁸ Early modern Catholic Jesuit philosophers, including Francisco Suarez (1548-1617), with whose writings Lynch was familiar, held an opinion that the temporal starting-point of a particular regime or dynasty did not define its nature and deprive it of present legitimacy, even if it was established by force, tyranny or usurpation.⁵⁹

Justification of the English kings' title over Ireland also relied on the theory of prescription. Lynch extracted quotations from various authors, including Bodin, Grotius, and Suarez, which confirmed that uninterrupted

⁵⁶ Richard O'Ferrall, Robert O'Connell, *Commentarius Rinuccinianus, de sedis apostolicae legatione ad foederatos Hiberniae catholicos per annos 1645-9*. Volumen quintum: ann. 1652-1666, ed. Stanislaus Kavanagh (Dublin: Irish Manuscripts Commission, 1944), 499-504.

⁵⁷ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 42, 46-8.

⁵⁸ René D'Ambrières, Éamon Ó Ciosáin, "John Lynch of Galway (c. 1599-1677): His Career, Exile and Writing", *Journal of the Galway Archaeological and Historical Society* 55 (2000), 50-63, at 51.

⁵⁹ E.g. Francisco Suarez, *Tractatus de legibus ac Deo legislatore* (Coimbra: Apud Didacum Gomez de Loureyro, 1612), l. III, cap. I, 200. On Jesuit thought on the origin of political authority cf: Harro Höpfl, *Jesuit Political Thought: The Society of Jesus and the State, c. 1540-1630* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004), 192-5, 228-55.

FELIKS LEVIN

inheritance of sovereignty originally obtained by force over a long period of time transformed the descendants of the usurpers into the lawful sovereigns if they did not encounter opposition and gained tacit consent of the people.⁶⁰ Recourse to the theory of prescription enabled Lynch to underline that the illegitimacy of the twelfth-century conquest could not impinge on the political legitimacy of the current dynasty:

. . . *suprema Hiberniæ potestas jam quingentos pene annos penes Angliæ reges existens, quamvis initio nequiter eam sibi vendicaverint, omnem primæ injuriæ maculam abstersit.*

. . . almost five hundred years of possessing the sovereignty of Ireland by the English kings, although having been primarily claimed in a faulty way, has wiped out every stain of original injustice.⁶¹

Similarly to Keating, Lynch justifies the legality of the Old English presence in Ireland through reference to the updated principle of nationality defined by birth and residence in Ireland rather than by ancestry. Arguing with the likes of O’Sullivan Beare and particularly O’Ferrall, he discards the genealogical criterion of nativeness. According to Ian Campbell, Lynch’s theory of ethnogenesis was inspired by Jean Bodin.⁶² In the later treatise *Alithinologia*, Lynch, quoting from *Methodus*, argues that all nations were the products of migration, colonization, and fusion of disparate peoples, comparing the Irish with the Italian multi-ethnic nation which was forged out of the mingling of diverse peoples.⁶³

In *Cambrensis Eversus*, the legitimization of the Irishness of the colonists is actually embedded in imperial discourse. Lynch mentions earlier precedents of successful imperial conquests which ensured harmonious relationships between the colonizers and the colonized and led

⁶⁰ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 42-4, 48-50; Bodin, *Les six livres*, b.II, c.V, 208; Suarez, *Tractatus de legibus*, l. III, c. IV, 207; Grotius, *De jure belli*, l.II, c. IV, 131.

⁶¹ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 38. Translation is my own.

⁶² Campbell, “Alithinologia: John Lynch,” 198-200.

⁶³ Jean Bodin, *Methodus ad facilem historiarum cognitionem* (Paris: Apud Martinum Juvenem, 1566), c. IX, 440; Lynch, *Alithinologia sive veridica responsio ad invectam mendaciis* (St Malo: S.n., 1664), 7.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

to ethnic fusion in the course of time. For instance, he recounts how the German tribe of the town of Ubia rejected the demand of the Tenterii, another Germanic tribe, to kill their Roman neighbours, who had recently established a colony there, on account of their intimate kin relations with the conquerors. He uses this example to pose a rhetorical question:

Quando autem Romani, et Ubii triginta solummodo annorum insitione in unam gentem coaluerunt: Nonna quingentis ferme annis ea vis inerit, ut ex Hibernis et Anglis unam gentem conflare possint?

If the Romans and the Ubians merged into one nation after only 30 years of grafting, are not 500 years powerful enough to make one people of the English and the Irish?⁶⁴

Lynch argues that the original point of violence standing behind the establishment of a multi-ethnic nation is irrelevant provided that the victors and the vanquished have cohabited with one another for a long time and are united by bonds of friendship to such an extent that it is impossible to distinguish between them.⁶⁵

Lynch refers to the Roman law to support Old English claims to having rights and property in Ireland. He appeals to Roman concepts of citizenship and *patria* (fatherland) which were open to immigrants and foreigners to legitimize the status of Old English as natives in Ireland.⁶⁶ Lynch foregrounds the political and legal connotations of *patria* asserting that a true fatherland is defined by the country of birth (*nativitas*), not the country of ancestral origins (*origo*).⁶⁷ He relies on Cicero's *On the Laws* 2.5, in which the Roman lawyer observed two kinds of *patria* for citizens of municipal towns, one generated by birth and the other by citizenship. Translating this concept to the Irish case, Lynch explains the right of both the first Anglo-Norman colonists and their subsequent descendants to consider Ireland their fatherland: the former could do it on the basis of

⁶⁴ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 160. Translation is my own.

⁶⁵ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 146, 150-60.

⁶⁶ See e.g. Jed Atkins, *Roman Political Thought* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 65-73.

⁶⁷ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 162.

enfranchisement, whereas the latter on account of their birth.⁶⁸ Also employing other concepts from Roman law, such as *incola* (inhabitant) and *domicilium* (dwelling), Lynch adds that regardless of the country of one's birth, a person can obtain native status in a certain territory by acquiring a property or residing there.⁶⁹ Cambrensis Eversus' legal understanding of nativeness and nationality glosses over ethnic distinctions and tensions resulting from the invasion between the Old English and the Gaels: both being subjects of the Stuart king, they share one fatherland where they can perform their civic duties and obtain legal rights and Irish identity.⁷⁰

Another strategy of (de)legitimizing the violent seizure of power in *Foras Feasa* and *Cambrensis Eversus* was through consensual theory. Keating emphasizes that rulers in Ireland, including Henry II, obtained consent from its people. He utilizes such words as *tol* (will); *togha* (election); *deóin* (consent) to denote popular acknowledgment of the ruler.

I d-Teamhraigh do gairthí gach rí do ríoghaibh Éireann riamh ag a mbíodh ríoghacht Éireann uile, do thoil na n-ollamhan is na n-uasal rí gcreideamh, agus do thoil eagailse uaisle is ollamhan ó shoin anuas, ar Leic na Ríogh.

It was at Tara on Leic na Ríogh that every one of the kings of Ireland who possessed the kingdom of all Ireland, by the consent of the ollamhs and of the nobles, used to be inaugurated before the Faith, and by the consent of the Church and of the ollamhs ever since the Faith.⁷¹

. . . do bhrigh nach léaghthar san seanchus go raibhe aoinrí ar Éirinn riamh ó aimsir Shláinghe go Gabhaltas Gall acht rí tháinig lé togha an phobail agus lé harrachtas a ghníomh is lé neart a láimhe i gceannus Éireann.

⁶⁸ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 168.

⁶⁹ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 166-8.

⁷⁰ See more on this issue: Levin, "'For Others Pergamum Has Been Overthrown; for Me Alone it Still Stands': Reflections on Conquest and Migration in Neo-Latin Histories of Ireland," in *Irish Migrations and Classical Antiquity*, ed. Isabelle Torrance (London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2026), 96-9.

⁷¹ *FFÉ*, III, 11-2.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

. . . since we do not read in the seanchus that there was ever any king of Ireland, from the time of Slainghe to the Norman Invasion, but a king who obtained the sovereignty of Ireland by the choice of the people, by the excellence of his exploits, and by the strength of his hand.⁷²

An tan iomorro adchuala Ruaidhrí Ó Conchubhair, rí Connacht is Éireann, a chúigeadhaigh is an lucht cíosa is cánachais do bhí aige, is an lucht da dtug féin tuilleamh is tuarastal, do dhul ar scáth ríogh Sacsan, do mheas 'n-a mheanmain féin go madh lughá do mhasladh dó umhla do thabairt da dheoin ioná da aimhdheoin uaidh do rígh Sacsan.

Now when Ruaidhri O Conchubhair, king of Connacht and of Ireland, heard that his provincial kings and those who paid him rent and tribute, and those to whom he himself gave wages and stipends, had put themselves under the protection of the king of England he judged in his own mind that it would be less an indignity for him to submit to the king of England voluntarily than to do so against his will.⁷³

Although Keating's source cannot be identified precisely, he may have found this political vocabulary⁷⁴ as well as consensual theory of kingship in native sources. Irish medieval legal tracts and annals reflected an idea of accession to power by will of the people, referring to nobility, clergy and learned men or, in a more general sense, to the people of a particular kingdom who ordained or elected their rulers.⁷⁵ Cunningham believes that

⁷² *FFÉ*, III, 182-3.

⁷³ *FFÉ*, III, 342-3.

⁷⁴ See, e.g., Bartholomew Maccarthy (ed), *Annala Uladh. Annals of Ulster; otherwise, Annala Senait, Annals of Senait; a chronicle of Irish affairs A.D. 1379-1541*, 1430.3, 110; 1432.1, 118, accessed 21 November, 2024, <https://celt.ucc.ie/published/G100001C/index.html>. Keating might not have access to the Annals of Ulster but could have met these concepts elsewhere.

⁷⁵ Simms, *From Kings to Warlords*, 44, 46; Thomas M. Charles-Edwards, "A Contract between King and People in Medieval Ireland? *Críth gablach* on Kingship," *Peritia* 8 (1994), 107-19, at 108-11; Katharine Simms, "The Contents of Later Commentaries

Keating's representation of the Irish kingship as elective and contractual was informed by Irish primary sources.⁷⁶ However, Keating's understanding of elective monarchy merits closer consideration. The people are not represented as kingmakers in the narrative. They inaugurate rather than appoint new rulers. In my opinion, in invoking the concept of the people's consent Keating means the popular acclamation which strengthened a king's claim to kingship.

I argue that Keating's rendering of consensual theory was influenced by early modern Second Scholasticism. For instance, Robert Bellarmine and Francisco Suarez with whose writings Keating may have been familiar⁷⁷ emphasized that the polity was an artefact of will and consent.⁷⁸ They developed 'translation theory' which posited that the power of the ruler was not immediately from God. It was also mediated through the people who transferred the power to the ruler.⁷⁹ Moreover, Suarez, for example, stressed that the explicit expression of people's approval was not always necessary in some situations, including conquest and usurpation. It could emerge gradually over time without any specific event.⁸⁰ The idea of active and tacit consent enabled Keating to highlight the civility of pre-Anglo-Norman Ireland where the transfer of power, often acquired by force of arms, was authorized by the people. In addition to a noble descent, acknowledgment of the people confirmed the legitimacy of the king who seized the Irish throne, including Henry II, to whom the Irish lords voluntarily surrendered.⁸¹

on the Brehon Law Tracts," *Ériu* 49 (1998), 23-40, at 35-9; Jaski, *Early Irish Kingship*, 59-63.

⁷⁶ Cunningham, *The World of Geoffrey Keating*, 142-5.

⁷⁷ Cunningham, *The World of Geoffrey Keating*, 32-5. The college of Bordeaux in which Keating studied had strong Jesuit connections, even though it was not dominated by Jesuits.

⁷⁸ Quentin Skinner, *The Foundations of Modern Political Thought*, 2 vols; *The Age of the Reformation*, vol. 2 (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998), 161-6; Höpfl, *Jesuit Political Thought*, 248-52.

⁷⁹ Höpfl, *Jesuit Political Thought*, 225-32.

⁸⁰ E.g. Francisco Suarez, *Defensio fidei Catholicae et Apostolicae adversus Anglicanae sectae errores, cum responsione ad Apologiam pro iuramento fidelitatis et Praefationem Monitoriam Serenissimi Jacobi Angliae Regis*, 1613 (Coimbra: Apud Didacum Gomez de Loureiro, 1613), l. III, c. II.19-20, 223-4.

⁸¹ *FFÉ*, III, 344.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

The idea of popular consent was equally important for Lynch. Arguing with Gerald of Wales and his followers, he insisted that in spite of the absence of continuous hereditary succession, Gaelic Irish kingship followed certain rules, being an elective monarchy.⁸² Some of the narrative formulae which Lynch uses to introduce the accession to kingship imply the participation of the people: perfect passive participles ‘*salutatus*’ (having been greeted), ‘*collocatus*’ (having been placed), ‘*delatus*’ (having been conferred), ‘*institutus*’ (having been appointed).⁸³ Consent was central to the legitimacy of the Stuart dynasty. In *Alithinologia*, Lynch writes that James was publicly acclaimed by two houses of the Irish Parliament of 1613 in which Irish Gaels were also summoned to give consent to their ruler:

*Tum vero nullius unquam populi consentio Rege sibi
cooptando expressior; quam Hibernorum in Iacobo Reges
suo agnoscendo, extitit.*

Then indeed, the consent of no people ever showed itself in choosing a king for themselves so explicitly, as that of the Irish in acknowledging James as their king.⁸⁴

I agree with Campbell who emphasizes that Lynch as an adherent of the Bodinian theory of sovereignty could not accept the idea of sovereignty being vested in the people.⁸⁵ Lynch’s doctrine implies popular acclamation or acknowledgment of the ruler which could take different forms, including tacit consent. Therefore, Lynch’s understanding of Irish elective monarchy might have converged with that of Keating.

In both *Foras Feasa* and *Cambrensis Eversus* consent of the subjects distinguishes a legitimate forceful acquisition of power from a tyrannical one. Keating’s explanation of why Brian Ború was not a tyrant (*anfhlaithe*), cited above echoes the Aristotelian definition of tyranny. The Greek philosopher differentiates between kings ruling over willing subjects in accordance with law and tyrants who rule over unwilling subjects on the

⁸² *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 88, 490; *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 338.

⁸³ e.g. *Cambrensis Eversus*, I, 420, 454, 456, 460, 464; *Cambrensis Eversus*, II, 20, 26, 36.

⁸⁴ Lynch, *Alithinologia*, 27; Campbell, “Alithinologia: John Lynch,” 168.

⁸⁵ Campbell, “Alithinologia: John Lynch,” 168-9, 174-5.

basis of their own private interest and with the help of foreign troops.⁸⁶ A Scandinavian invader Turgesius exemplifies tyrannical behavior in *Foras Feasa*, seizing the throne without the acknowledgment of the subjects and ruling arbitrarily over them with the help of the Scandinavian army.⁸⁷

In his rendering of tyranny, Keating conflates an Aristotelian interpretation of this phenomenon with a native one. In medieval Ireland, there was a paradigmatic opposition between *anflaith* as a king making false judgments and neglecting his duties, and *firfhlaith* as a fair ruler.⁸⁸ Bart Jaski identifies an additional meaning of the word *anflaith*, denoting a person who aspires to a status but lacks necessary qualifications.⁸⁹ I hypothesize that Keating referred to Turgesius as a tyrant in this sense of the word, given that only the rule of foreign outsiders and social inferiors was represented as typical misrule in *Foras Feasa*.

Likewise, Lynch calls Turgesius and Cairbre Cinnchait, the king descending from the vassal tribe Aithechthúatha, tyrants.⁹⁰ However, he puts more emphasis on the arbitrary actions of the government than on the descent of the ruler. For instance, he condemns the tyrannical policies of Parliamentarians as well as of the Cromwellian and Restoration Government administration of Ireland, including the dispossession of the native population, their banishment and their alienation from power.⁹¹

Keating's and Lynch's attitude to tyrannicide was complex. On the one hand, they endorsed resistance to a person who claimed the throne or property by force without any legitimate reason, such as Scandinavian invaders, treacherous Anglo-Norman families, and social inferiors. On the other hand, both authors felt challenged to counter dominant associations

⁸⁶ Aristotle, *Politics*, trans. Harris Rackham (Harvard: Harvard University Press, 1932), 1251a, 251.

⁸⁷ *FFÉ*, III, 172, 176.

⁸⁸ Maxim Fomin, *Instructions for Kings: Secular and Clerical Images of Kingship in Early Ireland and Ancient India* (Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2013), 70-82, 141-3, 165-6, 193-5, 198-203.

⁸⁹ Jaski, *Early Irish Kingship*, 76.

⁹⁰ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 288, 334,

⁹¹ E.g. *Cambrensis Eversus*, I, 42, 52.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

of the Irish with rebelliousness,⁹² so they opted for promoting the inherent loyalty of the people of Ireland to the supreme authority.⁹³ It was particularly important for John Lynch who advocated for the cause of the Irish Catholic gentry, hoping for the restitution of lands confiscated in the 1650s.⁹⁴ He faced an uphill struggle since the blame for the 1641 uprising was placed squarely on an alleged Catholic conspiracy in Restoration Ireland.⁹⁵

Having received a Catholic education, Keating and Lynch generally favoured obedience to secular rulers irrespective of the validity of their titles and the manner of government. Keating hinted that the rulers were responsible only to God.

Is é fáth iomorro fá ríoghthar aon duine amháin ós cionn na bpuibleach is na gríoch ionnus go mbiadh gach aon 'n-a fhlaithes féin umhal dó, is gan ar breith do neach dhiobh freasabhra ná cur 'n-a aghaidh feadh a fhlaithis féin, agus a thuigsin gurab ó Dhia is codhnach agus is cumhachtach ós cionn cháich do horduigheadh 'n-a rígh ós cionn na bpuibleach é da bhfollamhnughadh, agus da réir sin go ndleaghair dóibh umhla do thabhairt dó is a thuigse gurab é an t-aoin-Dia céadna is codhnach ar neamh ar talmhain is ar ifreann tug an smacht soin dó, is gurab uaidh fuair flaitheas . . .

Now, the reason why one person is made king over people and over territories is in order that each one in his own principality should be obedient to him, and that none of them should have power to resist or oppose him during his sovereignty, and to have it understood that it was by God who is Lord and ruler over all that he has been appointed king over the peoples to govern them, and hence that they

⁹² Leerssen, *Mere Irish & Fíor-Ghael*, 46-9; Clare Carroll, *Circe's Cup: Cultural Transformations in Early Modern Writing about Ireland* (Cork: Cork University Press, 2001), 16-8.

⁹³ *FFÉ*, III, 368; *Cambrensis Eversus*, I, 32, 38-44, 74; *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 78-80, 86.

⁹⁴ Campbell, "Alithinologia: John Lynch," 86.

⁹⁵ Greaney, "History and Identity," 52-3.

FELIKS LEVIN

are bound to obey him and to bear in mind that it is the same only God who is Lord of heaven and of earth and of hell that gave him that authority, and that it was from Him he obtained sovereignty . . .⁹⁶

Responding to O'Mahony, who argued for deposing Charles and electing a native prince,⁹⁷ Lynch highlights that people are not so free to break contracts and rebel against a ruler whose title was acquired by unjust occupation.⁹⁸ By advocating non-resistance to both usurpers and legitimate rulers whose rule deteriorated into tyranny, Keating and Lynch follow the precept from the Pauline Epistle to the Romans 13:1: "Let everyone be subject to the governing authorities, for there is no authority except that which God has established."

Neither Keating, nor Lynch were full-blown contractualists. They believed that the monarch reigned by the will of their subjects but did not envisage the relationships between the ruler and the ruled as reciprocal, in contrast to their frequent portrayal in the medieval Irish legal tracts, sagas, and annals.⁹⁹ The scope of the political community's agency was quite restricted, except for the precedents of self-defense mentioned in *Cambrensis Eversus*. Lynch agreed with the Jesuit idea that the individual was allowed to protect oneself in the case of a threat to one's life and property.¹⁰⁰ According to Lynch, the events in Ireland in the 1640s represented this case because the seizure of power in England by Parliamentarians posed a threat to the lives and property of Catholics, so they rightfully resorted to arms for the sake of their own self-preservation.¹⁰¹

To conclude, Keating and Lynch normalized and de-exoticized the forceful acquisition of power in the Irish history blending perceptions derived from Irish Gaelic, Classical, and contemporary mainland European

⁹⁶ *FFÉ*, III, 8-10.

⁹⁷ Conor O'Mahony, *Disputatio apologetica de iure Regni Hiberniae pro Catholicis Hibernis adversus haereticos Anglos* (Frankfurt: typis Bernardi Govrani, 1645), 103-5.

⁹⁸ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 68.

⁹⁹ On reciprocal relationships between king and people in the medieval Irish text cf. Jaski, *Early Irish Kingship*, 47-9, 95-7; Fomin, *Instructions for Kings*, 167-8, 219.

¹⁰⁰ Höpfl, *Jesuit Political Thought*, 292-6.

¹⁰¹ *Cambrensis Eversus*, III, 86-90; 112-4.

CONQUEST AND USURPATION

sources, particularly the works of the Jesuits, Jean Bodin and Hugo Grotius. The media in which Keating and Lynch wrote their narratives and the intellectual traditions they were engaged with supplied them with discursive templates through which they could interpret violent overtakings of the Irish throne and property. Moreover, their strategies of vindicating Irish history may have also depended on the expectations of the putative audiences of the narratives. Hence, Keating's strategy of explaining violence in Irish history took advantage of native narrative conventions and motifs and relied on the peculiarities of national history. Lynch, taking a European audience into account, made constant struggle for the throne and property in Ireland intelligible through a comparative approach and legal rendering of the issue.

Keating and Lynch insisted that conquests and forceful acquisitions of power were natural to Irish and world history. They formulated theories of conquest and the acquisition of power which they applied selectively to the precedents of violence in Irish history. Both authors distanced the Irish Gaelic past from accusations of barbarism, demonstrating that alternative ways of royal succession were not deprived of political legitimacy. With regard to the Anglo-Norman invasion and subsequent history of Ireland, Keating and especially Lynch dissociated the legality of the English title and colonial landholding from the morally questionable foundations of the Anglo-Norman conquest. By evoking theories of prescription and popular consent, they legitimized Stuart claims to the Irish throne and by appealing to the territorial principle of nationality, Old English claims to property in Ireland. In theorizing the violent seizure of power in Ireland before and after the Anglo-Norman conquest in such a way, both Keating and Lynch refuted colonial discourse about their country and criticized contemporaneous English rule while simultaneously fostering loyalty to the Stuart dynasty and transcending divisions in the Catholic camp.

Acknowledgments

This research has been supported by a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (PF) under contract number 101105224.